

IDENTIFICATION OF STIFFNESS AND DAMPING PROPERTIES FROM FORCED VIBRATING PLATES

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ABSTRACT : This paper presents a novel methodology for the identification of damping of isotropic plates. It can be extended to the anisotropic case. It relies on forced inertial excitation of a clamped plate and full-field curvature measurements using a suitable optical technique. Using the Virtual Fields Method, it is shown that the damping parameter is easily related to the curvature field, even on a non-resonant plate. This paper opens a totally new field of investigation for damping identification.

KEYWORDS : Identification; Virtual Fields Method; Damping; Forced vibrations; Plates

INTRODUCTION

Identification of damping is essential for the computation of stress and strains in vibrating structures. This parameter is often obtained from unsteady vibrations of beams. Nevertheless, intrinsic material behaviour is usually difficult to separate from damping arising from boundary conditions. This paper presents a novel procedure to identify stiffness and damping parameters of isotropic thin plates provided that full-field curvature measurements are available at the surface of the plate. It is based on the Virtual Fields Method [1, 2] and is an extension of initial work by Grédiac *et al.* [3, 4].

THEORY

For a solid of any shape, in the case of small perturbations, the general expression of the principle of virtual work writes:

$$-\int_V \sigma : \varepsilon^* dV + \int_{\partial V} F u^* dS = \int_V a u^* dm \quad (1)$$

where σ is the stress tensor, ε^* is a virtual strain tensor, V is the volume of the solid, ∂V the surface of its boundary, F the surface density of external forces acting on ∂V , u^* is a kinematically admissible virtual displacement field associated to ε^* and a is the acceleration field. dV , dS and dm are respectively elementary volume, surface and mass.

CONSIDERED CASE

Let us consider now that the solid is a rectangular thin plate. Its thickness is h (Figure 1). The plate is clamped in point O as seen in Figure 1, which is the origin of the coordinate system. Let us now suppose that this point is translated along the z axis in a sine movement (inertial excitation). This arrangement is an extension of the experimental study of vibrating plates reported in [5]. If we call $\delta(t)$ the displacement of this point along the z direction, and using usual complex notations, then:

$$\delta(t) = d \cdot \cos \omega t = \text{Re}(d \cdot \exp(j\omega t)) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Considered plate

where ω is the pulsation and d is the amplitude of the sine movement. For a homogeneous material, this is a case of pure bending and only out-of-plane displacements will be considered. Assuming classical thin plate theory, they are independent on z . The global out-of-plane displacement field $\mu(x,y,t)$ is therefore the superposition of the imposed excitation displacement $\delta(t)$ and the out-of-plane deflection $\lambda(x,y,t)$ due to the deformation of the plate:

$$\mu(x, y, t) = \delta(t) + \lambda(x, y, t) \quad (3)$$

The deflection caused by the deformation of the plate is made up of the combination of the response of each mode:

$$\mu(x, y, t) = \delta(t) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k(x, y, t) \quad (4)$$

where $\lambda_k(x,y)$ is the response of the k^{th} mode. Since the excitation has a sine shape and assuming the linear behaviour of the plate, the response is harmonic with the same pulsation ω :

$$\mu(x, y, t) = \delta(t) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |\lambda_k(x, y)| \cos(\omega t - \phi_k(x, y)) \quad (5)$$

where $|\lambda_k(x, y, t)|$ and $\phi_k(x, y)$ are respectively the amplitude and the phase of the response of the k^{th} mode. Because of the damping, the latter can take all the values between 0 and π , depending on the distance between the excitation and the k^{th} mode frequencies. Using complex notation it is easier to write:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Re}(u(x, y). \exp(j \omega t)) &= \text{Re}((d + \omega(x, y)). \exp(j \omega t)) \\ u(x, y) \in \mathbb{C}; u(x, y) &= u_r(x, y) + j u_i(x, y) \\ w(x, y) \in \mathbb{C}; w(x, y) &= w_r(x, y) + j w_i(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In the case of a plate having sufficiently separated modes and excited close to its k^{th} mode frequency, the response is dominated by that of the resonant mode which amplitude becomes predominant and which phase comes close to $\pi/2$. This contribution is mainly represented by the imaginary part $w_i(x, y)$. The response linked to the other modes have relatively small amplitudes and their phases are close to 0 or π . They are mainly represented by the real part $w_r(x, y)$. One could think these latter contributions could be negligible. In fact it depends on the considered mode and on the importance of the damping. The figures below show the representations of some conservative mode shapes and operational deflection shapes, real and imaginary parts, of the FE model used in section *Validation*. A heavy proportional damping is assumed for this simulation.

Figure 2: First mode and operational deflection shapes at first resonance

In Figure 2 the frequency of the harmonic excitation is close to the first mode frequency. The imaginary part of the response consists only in the first mode. The real part is only a solid out of plane displacement corresponding to the driving movement.

Figure 3: Third mode and operational deflection shapes at third resonance

For an excitation close to the third mode frequency, Figure 3 shows that the contributions of non resonant modes are not negligible in the imaginary part of the response and the contributions of several modes are significant in the real part. Obviously these are due to the damping coupling effect. A correct expression of the harmonic response of the vibrating plate must take into account the contributions of a great number of modes even close to a resonance and even with well separated resonant frequencies.

The proposed expressions for $u(x,y)$ and $w(x,y)$ provide complete representations of the harmonic responses and are even verified out of resonances.

CHOICE OF THE VIRTUAL FIELDS

The virtual displacement fields must be kinematically admissible. In particular, it means that they should be such that the virtual movement of point O must match its true movement. For instance, one can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} u^*(x,y).\exp(j\omega t) &= (d + w^*(x,y)).\exp(j\omega t) \\ y^*(x,y) &\in C; w^*(x,y) \in C \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where $w^*(x,y) = w_r^*(x,y) + jw_i^*(x,y)$ is a virtual deflection field, with $w^*(0,0) = 0$. As mentioned in the following section, u^* must be such that the clamping moments do not work virtually. Therefore, one must have:

$$\frac{\partial w^*}{\partial x}(0,0) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial w^*}{\partial y}(0,0) = 0 \quad (8)$$

VIRTUAL WORK OF EXTERNAL FORCES

The only external forces acting on the plate are that introduced by the clamping at point O (see Figure1). If there is a chance to measure experimentally the force acting in the z direction, the two bending moments M_x and M_y will be unknown and their contribution to the virtual work of the external forces will have to be zeroed by choosing appropriate virtual fields (see section *Choice of the virtual fields*). Let us consider now only F , the force in the z direction. It can be written as:

$$F \cdot \exp(j\omega t) = (F_r + jF_i \cdot \exp(j\omega t)) \quad (9)$$

Therefore, the virtual work of the external forces VW_{EF} simply writes:

$$VW_{EF} = \text{Re}(F \cdot \exp(j\omega t)) \cdot \text{Re}(d \cdot \exp(j\omega t)) \quad (10)$$

Developing the above, it can be shown that:

$$VW_{EF} = \frac{1}{2} F_r d + \frac{1}{2} \text{Re}(F d \cdot \exp(j2\omega t)) \quad (11)$$

Finally, it comes:

$$VW_{EF} = \frac{1}{2} F_r d + \frac{1}{2} F_r d \cdot \cos(2\omega t) - \frac{1}{2} F_i d \cdot \sin(2\omega t) \quad (12)$$

It can be seen that VW_{EF} is composed of three distinct terms, one independent from time and the two others depending on sine and cosine of twice the excitation pulsation.

VIRTUAL WORK OF THE INTERNAL FORCES

The virtual work of the internal forces (VW_{IF}) is written according to the Love-Kirchhoff theory of thin plates. In the case of dissipative materials, VW_{IF} can be written as the sum of an elastic and a dissipative contributions. One has:

$$VW_{IF} = - \int_S (\{m^e\} + \{m^d\}) \{\kappa\}^* dS \quad (13)$$

where $\{m^e\}$ and $\{m^d\}$ are respectively the elastic and dissipative moments and $\{\kappa\}^*$ is the virtual curvature field resulting from the virtual displacement field described in section *Choice...* It is important to note at this stage that the three above quantities are complex.

In the case of an isotropic and homogeneous material:

$$\{m^e\} = \begin{bmatrix} m_x^e \\ m_y^e \\ m_s^e \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{xx} D_{xy} & 0 \\ D_{xy} D_{xx} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (D_{xx} - D_{xy})/2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_x \\ k_y \\ k_s \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

where D_{xx} and D_{xy} are the isotropic

bending stiffness components of the plate.

Assuming that the dissipation is viscous and that the dissipative moment is proportional to the elastic one, one can write:

$$\{m^d\} = \beta \frac{\partial \{m^e\}}{\partial t} = j\beta\omega \{m^e\} \quad (15)$$

It is important to note that the method could be used with other formulations of damping. The one chosen here is kept as simple as possible to demonstrate the method. It can be shown that equation 13 can be written as:

$$VWIF = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{Re} \left(\int_s (\{m^e\} + \{m^d\}) \overline{\{k\}}^* dS \right) + \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{Re} \left(\int_s (\{m^e\} + \{m^d\}) \{k\}^* \cdot \exp(j2\omega t) dS \right) \quad (16)$$

here $\overline{\{k\}}^*$ indicates the conjugate of the virtual curvatures.

Using equations 14 and 15 to replace in equation 16, one can define the functions $H_{p,q}$ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{p,q}(x,y) = & -D_{xx} \int_s \left(k_x(x,y) k_x^* + k_y(x,y) k_y^* + \frac{1}{2} k_s(x,y) k_s^* \right) dS \\ & - D_{xy} \int_s \left(k_x(x,y) k_y^* + k_y(x,y) k_x^* - \frac{1}{2} k_s(x,y) k_s^* \right) dS \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where p and q indicate that the $H_{p,q}$ functions are calculated using:

- the real or imaginary parts of the actual curvatures depending whether to p is r or i ;
- the real or imaginary parts of the virtual curvatures depending whether to q is r or i .

Therefore, $VWIF$ can be expressed using are four H functions: $H_{r,r}$, $H_{i,i}$, $H_{r,i}$, $H_{i,r}$.

Finally, one has:

$$\begin{aligned} VWIF = & \frac{1}{2} \left[(H_{r,r} - \beta\omega H_{i,r}) + (H_{i,i} + \beta\omega H_{r,i}) \right] \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \left[(H_{r,r} - \beta\omega H_{i,r}) + (H_{i,i} + \beta\omega H_{r,i}) \right] \cos(2\omega t) \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \left[(H_{r,r} + \beta\omega H_{i,r}) + (H_{r,i} + \beta\omega H_{i,i}) \right] \sin(2\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

VIRTUAL WORK OF THE INERTIAL FORCES

Taking into account equation 6, the acceleration a writes:

$$a(x,y) \cdot \exp(j\omega t) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} (u(x,y) \cdot \exp(j\omega t)) = -d\omega^2 \cdot \exp(j\omega t) - w(x,y)\omega^2 \cdot \exp(j\omega t) \quad (19)$$

Moreover, $dm = \rho h dS$ where ρ is the density of the material. Therefore, the virtual work of the inertial forces $VWAC$ writes:

$$VWAC = -\frac{\rho h \omega^2}{2} \operatorname{Re} \left(\int_s u(x,y) \bar{u}^*(x,y) dS \right) - \frac{\rho h \omega^2}{2} \operatorname{Re} \left(\int_s u(x,y) u^*(x,y) \cdot \exp(j2\omega t) dS \right) \quad (20)$$

where $\bar{u}^*(x,y)$ indicates the conjugate of the virtual displacement field. Finally, it comes:

$$\begin{aligned} VWAC = & -\frac{\rho h \omega^2}{2} \int_s (u_r u_r^* + u_i u_i^*) dS \\ & - \frac{\rho h \omega^2}{2} \int_s (u_r u_r^* - u_i u_i^*) dS \cdot \cos(2\omega t) \\ & + \frac{\rho h \omega^2}{2} \int_s (u_r u_i^* + u_i u_r^*) dS \cdot \sin(2\omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

SUMMARY

Following the above calculations, the principle of virtual work writes:

$$VWIF + VWEF = VWAC \quad (22)$$

with the expressions for $VWIF$, $VWEF$ and $VWAC$ given in the previous sections. As shown previously, each contribution is written as the sum of a term independent on time and two terms dependent on sine and cosine of twice the excitation pulsation. Since the above equality is verified for any time, then it can be split into three separate equations. Moreover, the expressions are valid for any combination of the real and imaginary parts of the virtual fields. As a consequence, each of the three equations can again be split into two equations, leading finally to a system of six equations, from which only four are independent. These equations are given below.

$$H_{r,r} - \beta \omega H_{i,r} + F_r d = -\rho h \omega^2 \int_s u_r u_r^* dS \quad (23)$$

$$H_{i,i} + \beta \omega H_{r,i} = -\rho h \omega^2 \int_s u_i u_i^* dS \quad (24)$$

$$H_{i,r} + \beta \omega H_{r,r} + F_i d = \rho h \omega^2 \int_s u_i u_r^* dS \quad (25)$$

$$H_{r,i} + \beta \omega H_{i,i} = -\rho h \omega^2 \int_s u_r u_i^* dS \quad (26)$$

Since $u(x,y) = d + w_r(x,y) + jw_i(x,y)$ and $u^*(x,y) = w_r^*(x,y) + jw_i^*(x,y)$, the above system can be rewritten as:

$$H_{i,i} + \beta\omega H_{r,i} = -\rho h \omega^2 \int_S w_i w_i^* dS \quad (27)$$

$$H_{r,r} - \beta\omega H_{r,i} = -\rho h \omega^2 \int_S (d + w_r) w_r^* dS \quad (28)$$

$$F_r = -\rho h \omega^2 \int_S (d + w_r) dS \quad (29)$$

$$F_i = -\rho h \omega^2 \int_S w_i dS \quad (30)$$

VALIDATION

Forced vibrations of a plate with the conditions described in section *Considered case* have been simulated using finite element analysis. The model consists in 2048 shell elements. The numerical parameters of the model are reported in Table 1.

L (mm)	l (mm)	h (mm)	x ₀ (mm)	y ₀ (mm)	ρ (kg.m ⁻³)	E (GPa)	ν	d (mm)
200	100	1	50	25	7800	210	0.3	0.1

Table 1 : Parameters of the FE model

The harmonic responses of the FE model have been simulated for chosen frequencies of excitation and for two values of the damping coefficient: $\beta=10^{-5}$ (light damping) and $\beta=10^{-3}$ (heavy damping). The element curvatures and deflections are extracted, together with the coordinates of the elements centroids. Two virtual deflection fields are used: $w_1^*=x^2(1+j)$ and $w_2^*=y^2(1+j)$ (uniform virtual curvature fields).

To identify the three unknowns from equations 27 and 28, the following least-square objective function is built up:

$$f(D_{xx}, D_{xy}, \beta) = (H_{i,i} + \beta\omega H_{r,i} + \rho\omega^2 \int_S w_i w_i^* dS)^2 + (H_{r,r} + \beta\omega H_{i,r} + \rho\omega^2 \int_S (d + w_r) w_r^* dS)^2 \quad (31)$$

The integrals in $H_{p,q}$ are discretized using the finite element results and a simplex method is used to solve $f=0$.

The stability of the method with respect to the measurement noise has been tested. Random perturbations with normal distribution have been added to the element curvatures and deflections. As shown in the legends of the figures the levels of the perturbations have been chosen as percentage of the peak to peak values of the corresponding curvatures or deflections. The results are presented in terms of relative errors between the identified values and the reference values of the respective stiffness or damping. 30 calculations have been performed in each case to derive a distribution of identified values.

IDENTIFICATIONS AT RESONANCES

The frequencies of excitation have been chosen very close to those of the first four modes of the conservative plate.

Figure 4: Identification at resonance – Light damping ($\beta=10^{-5}$)

Figure 5: Identification at resonance – Heavy damping ($\beta=10^{-3}$)

IDENTIFICATIONS OUT OF RESONANCES

Since equations 27 and 28, used in the objective function, are verified for any excitation frequency, the identification method has been tested for 4 equally spaced chosen frequencies. The relative errors for the case of heavy damping are shown below.

Figure 6: Identification out of resonance – Heavy damping ($\beta=10^{-3}$)

Figure 6 shows results as interesting as those of Figure 5. Since in that case damping is important, the coupling effect caused by damping provides contributions of the non resonant modes. The harmonic response of the plate is important enough for correct identifications.

Obviously when the damping is low, there is no significant coupling effect between modes, the harmonic response out of resonance remains weak. In these conditions it is difficult to identify very little quantities like β in those conditions.

Due to the effect of integration in the $H_{p,q}$ expressions (see eq. 17) most of the results show very good stability over the measurement noise.

CONCLUSION

The main advantages of the method are:

- the method provides simultaneous identification of both stiffness and damping parameters;
- material damping is obtained, not modal damping;
- provided that the virtual fields are well chosen, the method will be insensitive to the clamping conditions;
- the plate can be of any shape;
- in case of heavy damping, the identification could be carried out at resonance and out of resonance.

The present method would certainly be a useful tool to investigate frequency dependence of damping. Moreover, future applications to anisotropic materials (composites) can be considered. Nevertheless, further investigation will be necessary to fully validate the method.

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